

Deliverable No. 2.7

Project acronym:
FarFish

Project title:
Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**
Project co-funded by the European Commission within the
Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1stJune 2017**
Duration: **54 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/05/2020
Submission date:	30/03/2022
File Name:	FarFish D2.7_ Report on the success of the self-sampling programme_4.0
Revision number:	04
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

Revision Control

Role	Name	Organisation	Date	File suffix
Main author(s) / Task Leader(s)	Karim Erzini	CCMAR	23/03/2022	KE
Authors	Duarte Fernández Vidal Gonzalo Machado-Schiaffino Carmen Blanco Fernández Ndiaga Thiam Fambaye Ngom Sow Mamadou Diallo Khallahi Brahim Kim Stobberup Jorge M.S. Gonçalves Mafalda Rangel	CETMAR U. Oviedo U. Oviedo CRODT CRODT COREWAM IMROP CCMAR CCMAR CCMAR	23/03/2022	DFV GMS CBF NT FNS MD KB KS JMSG MT
WP leader	Karim Erzini	CCMAR	23/03/2022	KE
Coordinator	Jónas R. Viðarsson	MATIS	30/03/2022	JRV
Administrative Coordinator	Oddur Már Gunnarsson	MATIS	30/03/2022	OMG

Deliverable D2.7

Report on the success of the self-sampling programme

30/03/2022

Executive Summary

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles. The FarFish project is designed around six case study areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast- and southwest Atlantic.

The overarching objective of the FarFish project is to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters, both within the jurisdiction of non-EU nations as well as international waters. In order to achieve this, the FarFish project has explored the applicability of implementing self-sampling programmes within EU long-distance fisheries and initiated a pilot self-sampling program as “proof of concept”.

The pilot self-sampling programme was implemented on board three Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) trawlers fishing for black hake (*Merluccius poli* and *Merluccius senegalensis*) in Mauritanian waters and Senegalese national vessels (Industrial and Artisanal). Sampling protocols and kits were provided by FarFish. The data collected includes fishing locations, dates, depth, visual identification of the species, sex and length. Fin clips were taken and stored in 100% ethanol. A total of 867 samples were obtained from three SFPA trawlers belonging to OPROMAR, the fishing vessel Kanbal of the SOPERCA company in Senegal, and artisanal longline vessels from Senegal. DNA analysis was carried out at the University of Oviedo.

Self-sampling was successfully carried out for all the fleets. However, results of the DNA analysis showed that mislabelling (misidentification) of black hake species is significant and variable, with differences between vessels of the same fleet (SFPA) and between the different sampled fleets (SFPA, Senegal Industrial and Senegal Artisanal). These differences may be explained in part by the geographic area and depth of the sampling location, with higher probabilities of misidentification in areas and depths where both species co-exist and are found together in the catches.

These preliminary results, along with the results of a follow-up questionnaire to eight self-samplers from Senegal suggest that self-sampling on board SFPA vessels is viable, cost-effective and can provide valuable data for improving stock assessment and management. However, in the case of the black hakes, training of self-samplers in morphological identification is essential if reliable fisheries and biological data is to be collected by self-samplers.

Abbreviations

CCMAR	Centro de Ciências do Mar
CECAF	Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy (EU)
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del Mar - Fundación CETMAR
CPUE	Catch Per Unit Effort
CRODT	Centre de Recherches Océanographiques de Dakar-Thiaroye
CS	Case Study
DCF	Data Collection Framework
EU	European Union
FPA	Fisheries Partnership Agreement
IEO	Spanish Institute of Oceanography
OPROMAR	La Organización de Productores de Pesca del Puerto y Ría de Marín
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement
TAC	Total Allowable Catches
WP	Work Package

Table of contents

1	INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT	6
2	MATERIALS AND METHODS	9
2.1	SAMPLING.....	9
2.2	DNA ANALYSES.....	12
2.3	FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONNAIRES.....	13
3	RESULTS.....	14
3.1	DNA ANALYSIS.....	14
3.2	QUESTIONNAIRES	18
3.2.1	<i>Senegal industrial fleet</i>	18
3.2.2	<i>Senegal artisanal fleet</i>	19
3.2.3	<i>SFPA vessels (OPROMAR)</i>	19
4	DISCUSSION	21
5	CONCLUSIONS.....	23
	REFERENCES	24
	ANNEXES.....	26

1 Introduction and context

In the EU, the Data Collection Framework (DCF) applies to all fisheries carried out by EU vessels, including those fishing outside EU waters under Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs). Although observer coverage of up to 100% has been achieved through collaboration with industry in some SFPAs, the observer coverage in most SFPAs is low. Lack of data for stock assessment and management of many stocks and species is a global problem. In this context, self-sampling schemes have been implemented in a wide range of commercial and recreational fisheries worldwide as a supplement to data collected by observers. Studies in the EU have shown that self-sampling can be a valuable and cost-effective method of data collection, with the added benefit of involving fishers in the scientific process of assessment and management of their fisheries. In EU fisheries, much of the self-sampling in recent years has been driven by the Common Fishery Policy (CFP) landing obligation (discards ban), where reference fleets (selected representative vessels chosen for the self-sampling scheme) apply self-sampling of catches and discards, with samples of the latter usually brought back to land for processing by fisheries scientists. Although not common, some self-sampling schemes have used fishers to collect samples for age and growth studies and even stomachs for analysis of diets.

Self-sampling schemes require volunteer fishers who are motivated and willing to carry out the extra work. Often, an incentive (e.g. financial, more days at sea, more quota) is required to guarantee fisher collaboration. Successful self-sampling programmes are based on mutual trust building between scientists and fishers, and discussion of the goals of the research, the data/sample collection methods and how the collected data/samples will be used. Data collection protocols must be followed, with clearly written instructions and forms used. Fishers need to be adequately trained in collecting data and biological samples in a consistent and standardized way, and they need to be provided with all the necessary materials for the sampling.

Implementing self-sampling in the FarFish case studies is an applicable approach to data gathering, in often otherwise data-poor areas. Full implementation of self-sampling programmes is however too complicated, time-consuming and expensive to be reachable within a research project like FarFish. The project has therefore initiated a pilot self-sampling program as “proof of concept” for species identification of black hake.

Three species of hake are found in north-west African waters: *Merluccius merluccius*, *Merluccius senegalensis* and *Merluccius polli* (Figure 1). The latter two species are important demersal resources in Mauritania and Senegal where they have overlapping distributions. The distribution of *M. senegalensis* ranges from 33°N to 10°N (Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017), while that of *M. polli* is wider, ranging from 25°N to 18.30°S (Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017). Thus, the two species overlap for over 2000 km, where they are fished jointly in a mixed fishery. There is also an overlap in their depth range:

M. polli is reported from 50 to 1,100m; and *M. senegalensis* from 15 to 800m (Froese and Pauly, 2021). There are small differences in the maximum and average sizes of both species, probably as a consequence of their different ecological strategies (Rey et al., 2015), with the average size (38.0 cm total length) of *M. polli* slightly smaller than that of *M. senegalensis* (42cm TL).

Black hakes are an important fishery resource. FAO (FAO, 2020) reports of black hake captures in the east central Atlantic (FAO zone 34) amounted to 29,547 tonnes in 2017, the last year with available data, of which 18,843t were reported as *M. senegalensis*, 4,677t as *M. polli* and the rest (6,027t) not specified. As one of the biggest importers, Spain reported a total of 13,847t landings in 2019 (Eurostat, 2021): 8,389t of *M. senegalensis*, 5,456t of *M. polli*, and the remaining 2t not specified.

Visual discrimination of these two species that are often mixed in catches is difficult and they are commonly marketed as “black hake” or *Merluccius* sp. Because of the difficulties in identification, stock assessment carried out within the framework of an FAO working group using production models is based on catch per unit effort data for both species combined. This makes species-specific management by quotas (TAC) impossible. Misidentification of captures has negative consequences in the sustainable management of the stocks, as the misrepresentation of the actual catch leaves one of the species underrepresented while the other is overrepresented (Cawthorn et al., 2018; Giovos et al., 2021). *Merluccius senegalensis* is classified as endangered in the International Union for Conservation of Nature –IUCN- Red List of Threatened Species (Iwamoto, 2015b), while *M. polli* is globally considered of least concern (Iwamoto, 2015a).

Figure 1: Map of the distribution of 12 species of hakes showing the overlap of the black hakes *Merluccius polli* and *Merluccius senegalensis* (adapted from Campo et al. 2008).

To improve stock assessment and management advice it is necessary to carry out species-specific stock assessment. Within the framework of the FarFish project it was proposed to use self-sampling by the

European fleet to collect data that could be incorporated into management tools. In FarFish D2.4 self-sampling programmes and templates were reviewed and evaluated (Erzini et al., 2019). The review showed that self-sampling is widely used as a practical and cost-effective way to collect data for stock assessment purposes and for assessing spatio-temporal patterns in species catch composition and discarding.

Given the importance of the black hake identification problem (FarFish D2.1, D2.4), it was decided to implement a pilot self-sampling programme using a fishing industry partner, OPROMAR and the Senegal case study partner CRODT. The objective was to test the capacity of the fishers to sample and identify the hake species. For evaluation of the identification of the species, FarFish collaborated with specialists in DNA analysis from the University of Oviedo, who processed and analysed the samples obtained from the self-sampling programmes. Here we report on the self-sampling programme and provide results of the analysis of the samples and the evaluation of the proportion of hake correctly identified on board Spanish trawlers of the OPROMAR company fishing in Mauritanian waters, and of samples take on board Senegalese national Industrial and Artisanal vessels.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Sampling

Sampling kits, sampling protocols and data sheets (in Spanish) were prepared at CCMAR and sent to CETMAR for delivery to OPROMAR for the two Spanish trawlers (A, B) participating in the self-sampling. The sampling kits (Figure 2) consisted of:

- 9 x 9 boxes of labelled micro-tubes filled with 100% ethanol
- Tweezers
- Scissors
- Ethanol and pads for cleaning tweezers and scissors
- Pencils and pencil sharpeners
- Clip boards
- Fish measuring boards (100 cm - not shown)
- Sampling protocol (Annex 1)
- Data sheets for each box, with an example (Annex 2)

Figure 2: Sampling kit (fish measuring boards not included) sent to OPROMAR via CETMAR.

Sampling protocols included visual demonstrations/explanations of the methodology to be used on board by the fishers (Figures 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7).

Self sampling on board trawlers

- Record the date, time, location and depth of the tow
- Randomly sample (30 black hake per tow if possible)
- Sample hake of different sizes
- **Important to include samples from depths/areas where both black hakes overlap**

Source of photo: ICM/CSIC (<http://www.dicat.csic.es/rdcsic/index.php/es/recursos-naturales-2/121-proyectos/356-un-proyecto-piloto-para-recuperar-las-poblaciones-de-merluza>)

Figure 3: Demonstration of sampling on board and the data to be recorded

Visual / morphological identification of species and measurement of total length (cm)

For each fish:

- Record the species
- Record the total length (cm) using the fish measuring board
- Record the sex (male, female, juvenile/immature)

Source of photo: MEDITS (<https://cobmedits2011.wordpress.com/2011/06/11/muestreo-de-tallas-2/>)

© FarFish

Figure 4: Demonstration of biological sampling and use of a fish measuring board to measure total length

Determination of sex

Record the sex of each individual by examining the gonads:

- Male
- Female
- Juvenile / immature

Source of photo: J. Lloret, G. Shulman & R. M. Love. 2014. *CONDITION AND HEALTH INDICATORS OF EXPLOITED MARINE FISHERIES*. 247pp. Published by Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford, U.K., ISBN:978-0-470-67024-8

Figure 5: Demonstration of biological sampling (determination of sex)

Fin samples for molecular based identification

- Cut approximately 1cm² of fin and place in labelled tube in ethanol
- Between samples, clean tweezers and scissors with pads soaked in ethanol

Figure 6: Demonstration of sampling of biological material (fin clip) for molecular based identification

Labelled micro-tubes should be placed in tube box and stored in a cool place

Figure 7: Demonstration of sampling of biological material (fin clips) for molecular based identification

In addition to the self-sampling on board the Spanish trawlers, the Senegal case study partners CRODT also agreed to carry out self-sampling on Senegalese vessels. Sampling kits were also sent to Senegal. The sampling plan initially included self-sampling on board trawlers of the fishing company SOPERCA but was extended to sampling on small-scale (artisanal) vessels fishing hake in the Kayar canyon, 54 km from Dakar, on the north coast. Samples of hake were taken by fishers on board the SOPERCA trawlers and by fishers on the small-scale fishing vessels but the data recording and the sampling for the DNA analysis was done by CRODT technicians.

2.2 DNA analyses

Reference samples from EU project MARINEGGS (QLK5-CT1999-01157) caught in 2000 along the coast of Senegal and identified de visu by IEO Cadiz experts were previously used to test the molecular markers employed in the identification. A total of 36 individuals of *Merluccius polli* and 35 individuals identified as *Merluccius senegalensis* were analysed. For reference samples, tissue was taken from the muscle.

For FarFish samples, tissue was taken from the fin. DNA was extracted with a DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit by QIAGEN. Mitochondrial Control Region was selected as the molecular marker, as this marker has been successfully used to identify different species of the genus *Merluccius* and due to its higher power of discrimination between both species over other markers (e.g. CO1 and CytB) (Machado et al., 2008). Primers MmerHK01 and MmerHK02 (Lundy, 2001) were used for an amplification of the Control Region

using 10 pmol of each primer, 1.5mM MgCl₂, 0.25mMdNTPs, 1x Buffer GoTaq®Promega, 0.15µl of GoTaq® Polymerase (5u/µL) and 2µL of DNA in a final volume of 20µL. PCR amplifications were performed in a thermo cycler ABI PCR 2700 (Applied Biosystems) with the following conditions: an initial denaturing step of 90°C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles consisting of 30s of denaturing at 90°C, 30s of annealing at 53°C for control region amplification, an elongation step for 45s at 72°C, and a final elongation step at 72°C for 15 min after the cycles.

PCR amplicons were visualized in 50ml agarose 2% gels with 2.5ml Simply Safe™ (EURX) and 4µl of amplified DNA. Control Region amplicons were sent for Sanger sequencing to Macrogen. Sequences were edited with Lasergene Seqman software by DNASTAR. Edited sequences were compared to Genbank sequence database, using BLAST (Basic Tool Alignment Search Tool) (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>).

Statistical analysis to find significant differences between both species and between correctly identified and mislabelled samples were performed in PAST4.03 software (Hammer, 2001). To analyze differences between hauls, vessels and sex Chi² Contingency test were performed. After testing normality, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Kruskal-Wallis test were chosen to evaluate differences between length, and Mann Whitney test was used for depth.

2.3 Follow-up questionnaires

Questionnaires were prepared in French and Spanish directed at the self-samplers on board the OPROMAR vessels and in Senegal (Example: Annex 3). The aims of the questionnaires were to evaluate the views of the fishers on the difficulties of collecting data, the identification of the black hakes, whether they were willing to participate in self-sampling programmes and if they thought the results of the study were useful for management of the fishery.

3 Results

3.1 DNA analysis

A total of 806 samples were successfully identified out of the total 813, leaving 7 samples unidentified (D39, D73, I86, J83, J84, J90). The samples were caught along the coasts of Mauritania and Senegal by different vessels from 28th November 2019 to 17th June 2020. All hakes had been identified on deck visually as *Merluccius senegalensis* (Cadenat, 1950), commonly known as Black Hake and *Merluccius polli* (Cadenat, 1950), commonly known as Benguela Hake. Data recorded for each sample included sex, and total length (cm) of the individual, geographic coordinates, depth, date, and time of capture. The geographic location of all samples off the coasts of Mauritania and Senegal can be seen in Figure 8, Catches discriminated by vessels can be seen in Figure 9, distribution of catches reported as *M. Polli* are shown in Figure 10 and distribution of catches reported as *M. senegalensis* are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 8: Distribution of all sampling locations.

Figure 9: Catches discriminated by vessel (Blue, OPROMAR Vessel 1; Purple, OPROMAR Vessel 2; Yellow, OPROMAR Vessel 3; Red, Senegal Industrial Vessels; Green, Senegal Artisanal Vessels).

Figure 10: Distribution of catches reported as *M. polli* (Blue, Correct labels; Pink, Mislabeled).

Figure 11: Distribution of catches reported as *M. senegalensis* (Red, Correct labels; Black, Mislabeled).

A total of 512 individuals were reported as *M. polli*, out of which, 198 were genetically identified as *M. senegalensis* (38.67% mislabelling); and a total of 294 individuals were reported as *M. senegalensis*, out of which, 54 were genetically identified as *M. polli* (18% mislabelling). Hakes were captured by OPROMAR trawlers along the coast of Mauritania (3 vessels N= 119, N= 158, N=81), and by Senegalese industrial (N=162) and artisanal vessels (N=286) along Senegal shores (Figure 9).

Mislabelling risk varies between vessels. On the coast of Mauritania, OPROMAR vessels 1 and 2 reported all their samples as *M. polli*. However, 16 individuals from Vessel 1 were identified as *M. senegalensis* by the DNA analysis, accounting for 13.45% of the total catch, as well as 43 samples from Vessel 2 (27.21% of total catch). Vessel 3 reported 66 *M. polli* and 15 *M. senegalensis*; within the latter, 2 samples were identified as *M. polli*.

Off the coast of Senegal, industrial vessels reported 53 *M. polli*, and 109 *M. senegalensis* captures. However, out of the reported *M. polli*, 23 were identified as *M. senegalensis*, accounting for a 43.4% of the *M. polli* samples, as well as 52 *M. polli* within the reported *M. senegalensis*, (47.8% of *M. senegalensis* catches), hence, mislabelled samples amount for a 46.29% of the total catch. Artisanal vessels reported 116 *M. polli* and 170 *M. senegalensis*; however, all samples were genetically identified as *M. senegalensis*, leaving a 40% of misidentified samples from the total. Hence, a significant directionality of mislabelling exists towards a higher number of unreported *M. senegalensis*

($X^2=35.828$; $p\text{-value}=2.15E-09$). Geographic distribution of samples identified as *M. polli* and *M. senegalensis* are given in figures 10 and 11.

Chi2 contingency test showed significant differences between vessels (MP: $X^2=266.75$, $p\text{-value}=1.6E-56$; MS: $X^2=101.08$, $p\text{-value}=1.12E-22$). Additionally, mislabelling risk in hauls within vessel 2 and within industrial vessels (PI) was significantly different (Vessel 2: $X^2=57.16$, $p\text{-value}=2.38E-12$; PI: $X^2=99.563$, $p\text{-value}=1.58E-14$, while no significant differences were found within artisanal vessels (PA) (PA: $X^2=6.73$, $p\text{-value}=0.15$) Analysis was not performed for Vessel 1 and 3 due to small number of hauls with an $N > 15$.

Differences between both hake species were found in length of individual and depth of capture. *M. senegalensis* were significantly smaller than *M. polli* in both females (average length (cm): MP= 49.57, SD= 9.33; MS= 48.35, SD=7.99) and males (average length (cm): MP= 41.65, SD= 7.41; MS= 39.26, SD=8.68), but not in juveniles (Females: $D=0.18$, $p\text{-value}=0.003$; Males: $D=0.22$, $p\text{-value}=0.02$; Juveniles: $D=0.2$, $p\text{-value}=0.32$).

Regarding accuracy of species reported, no significant differences were found between males, females or juveniles in either of the species except for *M. senegalensis* obtained from industrial fishing ($H=20.8$; $p\text{-value}=0.0001$), where mislabelling was higher in males (33% mislabelling in females vs. 59.01% in males). Length was significantly different between both species, and correct and incorrect species assignments ($H=55.96$; $p\text{-value}=4.25E-12$). Average length was higher for hakes reported as *M. polli*, regardless of accuracy (average length (cm): MP reported as MP: 48.83, SD=8.44; MS reported as MP: 47.21, SD=7.67; MS reported as MS, 35.4, SD= 8.01; MP reported as MS, 35.79, SD=3.77). Similarly, differences between depth distributions of both species are significant ($H=0.58$; $p\text{-value}=1.22E-36$), with a higher average depth for *M. polli* (average depth (m): MP: 467.65, SD=112.32; MS: 329.36, SD=122.41). This is consistent through all vessels, except for vessel 1 ($z=0.91$, $p\text{-value}=0.36$). No significant differences in depth distribution were found between correct and incorrect identified samples of the same species in any of the vessels.

Mislabelling is high overall, indicating a low level of discrimination between both species with the exception of vessel 3. Moreover, vessels 1 and 2, which only reported *M. polli* captures lower mislabelling risk consistent with the relative presence in their catches of *M. senegalensis*. In contrast, vessels belonging to artisanal and industrial fisheries from Senegal have higher mislabelling odds, despite reporting both species.

Table 1: Summary of accuracy of identifications according to DNA analysis

	Identified as	Correct	Incorrect	% Incorrect
OPROMAR Vessel 1	<i>M. polli</i>	103	16	13.4
	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	0	NA	NA
OPROMAR Vessel 2	<i>M. polli</i>	115	43	27.2
	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	0	NA	NA
OPROMAR Vessel 3	<i>M. polli</i>	66	0	0
	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	13	2	13.3
Senegal Industrial	<i>M. polli</i>	30	23	43.4
	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	57	52	47.7
Senegal Artisanal	<i>M. polli</i>	0	116	100.0
	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	170	0	0

3.2 Questionnaires

3.2.1 Senegal industrial fleet

Five self-samplers from the Senegal Industrial vessels, all crew members ranging in age from 25 to 40 (average 35), with 5 to 13 years (average 8 years) of work experience in the industry, were interviewed.

Four out of five reported having no difficulty in carrying out the self-sampling tasks. The majority (80%) rated their ability to distinguish the two species as high/good, with 4 on the 1 to 5-point scale, while the fifth interviewee rated his ability as average (3 on the 5-point scale).

Regarding the clarity of the questions, 4 of 5 interviewees selected 5 (very clear), while one selected 4 (quite clear). The same 4 crew members stated that the amount of work required was average (3/5), while the other crew member selected 2 (little work). Except for one crew member who selected 2 for the question on conditions on board facilitating the self-sampling, the average score for the rest was 4, indicating that conditions on board were good/favourable for self-sampling. The amount of time per tow spent sampling by each of the interviewees ranged from 2 to 20-30 minutes.

All the interviewees expressed a willingness to participate in future studies and to collect additional data. They all were interested in knowing the results of the pilot study and all preferred a meeting as the means of being informed, with one additionally selecting a report as the way he would also like to be informed. Three out of five were not willing to participate in a dissemination video.

All the interviewees believed that the self-sampling would contribute to improved fisheries management, but two were not willing to commit to future collaboration with scientists to develop self-sampling protocols based on their priorities.

3.2.2 Senegal artisanal fleet

For the Senegal artisanal (pirogue) fleet, two young crew members (15 and 16 years old) with 2- and 7-years' experience and a 35-year-old skipper with 20 years' experience were interviewed.

None had any difficulty with the tasks required for self-sampling, but ability of identify the black hake species was low for the two crew (1 and 2 on the 5-point scale), but good for the skipper (4 on the 5-point scale). While one of the crew found the instructions not clear (2 out of 5 on the scale), the other fisher and the skipper both found the instructions clear (4 and 5 on the scale, respectively). All the interviewees reported that the self-sampling involved a lot of work (4 to 5 on the 5-point scale) and there was no consensus regarding the conditions on board, with responses ranging from 3 to 5. All respondents misunderstood the question about the time needed to carry out the sampling, instead reporting the time taken to haul the longline gear.

All interviewees were willing to participate in future studies, collect other data and were interested in knowing the results of the study. They all preferred a meeting as a means of learning about the results. All agreed that the work would contribute to improved management. All were willing and available to collaborate with scientists in the development of self-sampling protocols based on their priorities.

3.2.3 SFPA vessels (OPROMAR)

Questionnaires were sent to the three OPROMAR vessels involved with the self-sampling activity. Five self-samplers from fresh fish industrial vessels catching black hake, all coastal skipper members ranging in age from 37 to 57 with 18 to 35 years of work experience in the industry, were interviewed. The three of them commented not having had any difficulties with the activity, although in some cases the lack of rest stands out as a determining factor in the development of the self-sampling activity.

Regarding the clarity of the questions, all interviewees showed instructions provided were very clear and they managed to fulfil all specific indications, although the reference to an excessive work was once again evident in the answers (heavy workload on board)

Related to the conditions on board facilitating the self-sampling, all the interviewees indicated that conditions on board were very favourable for self-sampling activity implementation. The amount of time per tow spent sampling by each of the interviewees ranged from 30 minutes to 2 hours.

All the interviewees expressed a willingness to participate in future studies and to collect additional data, although some of them showed their concerns about the low capacity for fishermen to influence decision-making.

They all were interested in knowing the results of the pilot study and all preferred a single template showing the main results. None of them were willing to participate in a dissemination video.

4 Discussion

Self-sampling on board Spanish (OPROMAR), Senegal Industrial and Senegal Artisanal vessels was successfully carried out. Data was correctly recorded on the data sheets and the quality of the samples for the DNA analysis was satisfactory, with only 7 (0.86%) of the analysed samples not amplifying correctly.

Interesting results were obtained based on the geographic and depth distributions of the two hake species, suggesting that the data can contribute important new information on geographic and bathymetric distribution. Previous studies based on visual identification suggest that there are differences in the depth distributions of the two species, with maximum overlap at depths of between 500 - 600m reported for Moroccan waters (Manchih et al., 2018). This is supported by the findings of the DNA analysis.

The percentage of mislabelling varied widely between the different fleets, within the vessels of the same fleet and for the two different species. Mislabelling of *M. polli* varied from 0% for OPROMAR vessel 3 to 100% for the Senegal Artisanal fleet. For *M. senegalensis*, mislabelling varied from 13.3% (OPROMAR vessel 3) to 47.7% for the Senegal Industrial vessels. It should be noted that not all 5 sampling units (OPROMAR vessels A, B and C, Senegal Industrial and Senegal Artisanal) caught both species. This is probably due to the sampling locations and depths. The results may therefore be influenced by these factors (geographic location and depth), with higher probabilities of mislabelling for samples taken from areas where both species co-occur.

These results suggest that despite the availability of the morphologically based guidelines developed by the IEO for the visual discrimination of black hake, there is still a significant misidentification of the black hake species. However, fishers who have not been trained in morphological identification using the IEO guidelines, such as the self-samplers on board artisanal fishing vessels, cannot be expected to be as proficient as self-samplers who have been trained to identify the two species of black hake.

In total, 865 samples were obtained, with 405 samples from three OPROMAR fishing vessels and 460 from Senegalese vessels. The total cost of the self-sampling kits provided was less than 200 €. The cost for the laboratory processing of the samples for molecular identification was 9,698.79 €. Including transport, the total cost of the molecular identification of 865 hake is less than 10,000€, or approximately 11€ per sample. We believe that this is a cost-effective method of obtaining a large amount of accurate data on black hake species composition in the Mauritanian and Senegalese fisheries. This will contribute to improving our understanding of the black hake fishery and to assessment for the individual species rather than analysis based on pooled data for the two black hake species, *M. polli* and *M. senegalensis*.

The questionnaire surveys of the self-samplers on board Industrial and industrial vessels from Senegal showed that members of the crew could reliably take samples for DNA studies and in the case of the OPROMAR vessels record necessary data. The latter was not possible on the Senegalese vessels, in part due to the conditions on board the small artisanal vessels and also due to the generally low educational level of the fishers.

In general, the sampling protocols were found to be clear, understandable and easy to follow. The amount of time needed to sample ranged from a few minutes to less than 30 minutes per sampling episode (i.e. trawl haul in the case of Industrial fleet trawlers), meaning that self-sample does not occupy a significant amount of time, which accounts for the majority of the self-samplers responding that they would be willing to continue self-sampling or other collaborations with scientists. Self-samplers were interested in the study, believing that the results would be important for the management of the fishery. All were interested in learning about the results of the study, preferably through a meeting.

Although this is a pilot study, we believe that it is already possible to conclude that self-sampling is a viable methodology for the particular problem of the black hake. This approach can provide extremely reliable data on the identification of the species. Based on self-sampling aboard the SFPAs vessels, the catch composition by species of hake can be extrapolated to the total catch. Thus, landings data can be provided by species of hake, rather than the generic category "black hake". From the fisheries management perspective, it can be envisaged that a self-sampling programme of this type can be incorporated in future national (Mauritania and Senegal) stratified demersal cruise surveys covering a vast area and wide depth range as well as SFPAs vessels. This will allow CPUE data to be obtained by hake species, thereby permitting stock assessment and determination of TACs at the species level, which will be a significant advance given the current situation. Seasonal, geographic and depth distributions can also be studied based on data collected from stratified demersal surveys. This is particularly relevant nowadays in light of climate change and possible changes in species distributions and recruitment. Molecular identification of black hakes can also be used on samples of landings, rather than on board fishing vessels. This would also provide information allowing catch composition by species to be estimated.

Training and resources for continuation of molecular analyses of landed fish after the end of the project was not foreseen in the FarFish project. The self-sampling study for DNA analysis was a pilot study to determine the feasibility of self-sampling and to evaluate the levels of misclassification in the different fleets exploiting black hakes. This issue was discussed with the case study partners who proposed a follow-up study that would enlarge the scope of the molecular studies and include training. With regard facilities and equipment for carrying out DNA analysis, it is not known what is available in Senegal. However, it is highly likely that the necessary equipment and facilities do indeed exist at

universities or national laboratories. The alternative would be to send the samples to Europe for analysis.

The potential for expansion/replication of this self-sampling approach is considerable. For example, many species of commercial shrimp are difficult to identify morphologically and the same self-sampling approach, with molecular identification could be used to obtain species-level information on size distributions, depth and geographic ranges, and relative abundance (CPUE) by species, contributing to improved stock assessment and management.

The main difficulties encountered in this pilot study were in the morphological identification of the two hake species. Thus, we recommend that training in morphological identification of potential self-samplers in any future study in order to guarantee high levels of accurate identification of sampled black hakes.

5 Conclusions

The main conclusions and implications of this pilot study are:

- Self-sampling proved to be viable and successful in all fleets (SFPA trawlers, Senegal industrial trawl and Senegal artisanal fleets) for obtaining high quality data for DNA analysis.
- High levels of misclassifications of the two species of hake were found in all fleets.
- Misclassification of black hakes prevents separate stock assessment for each species.
- The results suggest that training in morphological identification of black hakes is required in order to improve catch and effort data and allow stock assessment by species.
- Alternatively, a sampling programme of commercial landings for species identification by molecular analysis that will allow estimates of the contribution of each species to the total landings should be established.
- Self-sampling could be applied to other fisheries where the same problems exist with regard identification of morphologically similar commercial species, resulting in pooled catch data, making assessment of the state of different stocks impossible.
- While self-sampling in itself is relatively inexpensive, funding must be available for the molecular analysis (equipment, reagents, training and technicians).

References

- Campo, D., G. Machado-Schiaffino, J. PerezEva Garcia-Vazquez & E. Garcia-Vazquez. 2008. Phylogeny of the genus *Merluccius* based on mitochondrial and nuclear genes. *Gene* 406:171-9
- Campo, D., Machado-Schiaffino, G., Horreo, J. L., & E. Garcia-Vazquez. 2009. Molecular organization and evolution of 5S rDNA in the genus *Merluccius* and their phylogenetic implications. *J Mol Evol*, 68: 208–216.
- Cawthorn, D. M., Baillie, C., & S. Mariani. 2018. Generic Names and Mislabeling Conceal High Species Diversity in Global Fisheries Markets. *Conserv. Lett.* 11, 1–12.
- Eurostat 2021 Eurostat. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/fisheries/data> (Accessed 29 July 2021).
- FAO 2020. Fisheries and Aquaculture Software. FishStatJ - Software for Fishery and Aquaculture Statistical Time Series. In: FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture. Available at: <http://www.fao.org/fishery/> (Accessed 21 July 2020).
- FarFish. 2017. D2.1_Case study characterisation_V2.0, 84p.
- FarFish. 2018. D2.4_Templates and protocols for self-sampling. 31p + annexes.
- Fernández-Peralta, L., Quintanilla, L. F., & J. Rey, 2017. Overlapping Distribution of Two Sympatric Species: The Case of Black Hakes, *Merluccius polli* Cadenat 1960 and *Merluccius senegalensis* Cadenat 1960, Off Mauritania, in Deep-Sea Ecosystems Off Mauritania: Research of Marine Biodiversity and Habitats in the Northwest African Margin, 241–275.
- Froese, R., & Pauly, D. 2021. FishBase. Available at: www.fishbase.org (Accessed 28 July 2021).
- Giovas, I., Aga Spyridopoulou, R. N., Doumpas, N., Glaus, K., Kleitou, P., Kazlari, Z., et al. (2021). Approaching the “Real” State of Elasmobranch Fisheries and Trade: A Case Study From the Mediterranean. *Ocean Coast. Manage.* 211, 105743. doi: 10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105743
- Hammer, Ø., Harper, D. A. T., & Ryan, P. D. (2001). PAST : Paleontological Statistics Software Package for Education and Data Analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica*, 4(1), 1–9.
- Iwamoto, T. 2015a. “*Merluccius polli*,” in IUCN Red List Threat. Species 2015 E . T 1 5 5 2 2 2 2 6 A 1 5 6 0 3 6 1 0 . d o i : 1 0 . 2 3 0 5 / IUCN.UK . 2 0 1 5 -4.RLTS.T15522226A15603610.en
- Iwamoto, T. 2015b. “*Merluccius senegalensis*,” in IUCN Red List Threat. Species 2015 E.T15522229A15603615. do i : 10.2305/IUCN.UK.2015-4.RLTS.T15522229A15603615.en
- Lloret, J., G. Shulman & R. M. Love. 2014. CONDITION AND HEALTH INDICATORS OF EXPLOITED MARINE FISHES. 247pp. Published by Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford, U.K., ISBN:978-0-470-67024-8
- Chers collègues,
Pouvez-vous m'aider à répondre à ce commentaire des évaluateurs de FarFish Deliverable 2.7

Qui pourrait faire l'analyse ADN au Sénégal ? Y aurait-il un besoin de formation ?

Lundy, C. J., Rico, C., & Hewitt, G. M. 2000. Temporal and spatial genetic variation in spawning grounds of European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) in the Bay of Biscay. *Molecular Ecology*, 9, 2067–2079. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294X.2000.01120.x>

Machado-Schiaffino, G., Martinez, J. L., & Garcia-Vazquez, E. (2008). Detection of mislabeling in hake seafood employing mtSNPs-based methodology with identification of eleven hake species of the genus *Merluccius*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 56, 5091–5095. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf800207t>

Manchih, K., L. Fernández Peralta, J. Bensbai, A. Najd & M. Bekkali. 2018. Distribution of black hakes *Merluccius senegalensis* and *Merluccius polli* along the Moroccan Atlantic coast. *AAFL Bioflux*, 11:245-258. <http://www.bioflux.com.ro/aacfl>

Pendás, A.M., Morán, P., Freije, J. P. & E. García-Vázquez. 1994. Chromosomal mapping and nucleotide sequence of two tandem repeats of Atlantic salmon 5S rDNA. *Cytogenet Cell Genet* 67:31–36.

Rey, J., Fernandez-Peralta, L., Quintanilla, L. F., Hidalgo, M., Presas, C., Salmeron, F., et al. 2015. Contrasting Energy Allocation Strategies of Two Sympatric *Merluccius* Species in an Upwelling System. *J. Fish Biol.* 86, 1078–1097.

Annexes

Annex 1. Sampling protocol for Spanish trawlers (OPROMAR).

Protocolo de muestreo merluza negra para análisis de DNA.

1. Registre la ubicación, fecha, hora y profundidad de cada lance en la hoja de muestreo
2. Para cada lance, seleccione entre 30-40 merluzas, al azar de entre toda la captura): asigne un identificador único (código / número), identifique la especie por el método morfológico (visual) y registre la longitud total y el sexo.
3. Corte un trozo pequeño de aleta (aprox.1 cm²), a poder ser de la parte terminal de la aleta la cual contiene rayos más delgados y más tejido. Para la correcta preservación del ADN, es necesario que el tejido no represente más de aproximadamente 1/4 del volumen total (1/4 tejido y 3/4 de etanol).
Coloque el tejido en un microtubo con tapón a rosca.
Cada caja de almacenamiento de tubos será previamente rotulada con el rango de identificador único de los tubos que contiene, para facilitar su manejo durante el muestreo. Con el fin de evitar mezcla de muestras entre lances contiguos, se puede dejar una muestra vacía (sin muestra) entre lances.
4. Limpie / desinfecte las tijeras con etanol antes de tomar la siguiente muestra. Secar con un papel y verificar que no hay restos de tejido para evitar contaminaciones.
5. Guarde los tubos en un lugar fresco (e.g. nevera).
6. Envíe los tubos con la hoja de muestreo que contiene el identificador único, ubicación fecha, hora, profundidad, especie, sexo y datos de longitud total a CETMAR cuando los barcos regresen a Vigo.
7. Si transcurre mucho tiempo (semanas) entre la llegada a CETMAR y la extracción de ADN en Oviedo, es conveniente cambiar el etanol de cada tubo por etanol nuevo.
Si no transcurre mucho tiempo, esta tarea se hará en la Universidad de Oviedo.

Annex 2. Sampling protocol for Senegalese Industrial and Artisanal fishing vessels (CRODT).

Protocole d'échantillonnage du merlu noir pour l'analyse d'ADN.

1. Notez l'emplacement géographique (les coordonnées géographiques), la date, l'heure et la profondeur dans la feuille d'échantillonnage
2. Sélectionnez entre 20 et 30 merlus de chaque trait, au hasard parmi la totalité de la capture: attribuez un identifiant unique (F1, F2, etc.), identifiez l'espèce selon la morphologie (visuelle) et enregistrez la longueur totale et le sexe.
3. Coupez un petit morceau de nageoire caudale (environ 1 cm²) qui contient des rayons plus fins et plus de tissu. Pour la conservation correcte de l'ADN, il est nécessaire que le tissu ne représente pas plus d'environ 1/4 du volume total (1/4 de tissu et $\frac{3}{4}$ d'éthanol).
Placer le tissu dans un microtube avec bouchon à vis.
4. Nettoyez / désinfectez les ciseaux avec de l'éthanol avant de prélever l'échantillon suivant. Sécher et vérifier qu'il n'y a aucune trace de tissu pour éviter les contaminations.
5. Conservez les tubes dans un endroit frais (par exemple un réfrigérateur).
Exemple de feuille d'échantillon sur la page suivante.

Annex 3. Questionnaire directed to artisanal fishery (pirogue) self-samplers in Senegal. The same questionnaire in Spanish was used for the Senegal Industrial vessels and the OPROMAR vessels.

ENQUETE DE SATISFACTION SUR L'ACTIVITE D'AUTO-ECHANTILLONNAGE POUR AMELIORER L'IDENTIFICATION VISUELLE DES ESPECES 'MERLUCCIUS POLLI' ET 'MERLUCCIUS SENEGALENSIS'

AGE: ETUDE: <input type="checkbox"/> Supérieur <input type="checkbox"/> Degré moyen <input type="checkbox"/> Secondaire/FP <input type="checkbox"/> Diplômé <input type="checkbox"/> Sans étude Années dans profession: Rôle sur la pirogue :	Nombre d'équipage: LONGUEUR: CAPACITE DE CHARGE :(Indicar GT o TRB) ANNEE BATEAU:
--	--

Marquer avec un X et décrire brièvement lorsque cela est indiqué

1. Vous avez eu une certaine difficulté à effectuer le travail demandé?

SI NO

1a. Commentez brièvement les principales difficultés rencontrées

.....

2. Comment évalueriez-vous votre capacité à distinguer visuellement les deux espèces de merlu noir (*M. polli* y *M. senegalensis*)? (Faible 1 = Très peu/ 2 = Peu/ 3 = normal/ 4 = Assez/ 5= Beaucoup)

Connaissance du <i>merlu polli</i> (noir)	1	2	3	4	5
Connaissance du <i>merlu senegalensis</i> (sableux)	1	2	3	4	5

3. Évaluez les questions suivantes de 1 à 5 (Faible 1 = Très peu/ 2 = peu/ 3 = normal/ 4 = Assez/ 5= Beaucoup)

Les instructions fournies ont été claires	1	2	3	4	5
C'était beaucoup de travail	1	2	3	4	5
Les conditions du bateau ont facilité le travail à bord	1	2	3	4	5

4. Combien de temps par jour (par trait) avez-vous consacré à l'activité d'échantillonnage?

..... Heures/lance

5. Seriez-vous prêt à participer à un autre type d'auto-échantillonnage à bord?

SI NO

5a) Si la réponse est No , expliquez pourquoi?:

.....
.....

5b) Si la réponse est OUI; ¿ seriez-vous prêt à?:

5b1 ¿ Passez plus de temps au boulot qu' à collecter des échantillons? SI NO

5b2 ¿Collectez d'autres types de données ? SI NO

6. Souhaitez-vous connaître les résultats du travail effectué? SI NO

6a) Si la réponse est OUI, comment aimeriez-vous que les résultats soient communiqués? Choisissez toutes les options que vous envisagez

Réunion Rapport Borchure informatique Autres (les citer)

Autres.....

7. Seriez vous disposés de réaliser une vidéo (maximum 2 minutes) en racontant votre expérience?

SI NO

8. Vous considérez que le travail effectué est important pour favoriser la gestion des pêches?

SI NO

9. Pensez-vous que si le pêcheur aide en fournissant des informations, la gestion des pêcheries s'améliorerait? SI NO Expliquez brièvement

.....
.....

10. Vous souhaitez concevoir un protocole d'auto-prélèvement d'échantillons, en collaboration avec les scientifiques, en fonction de vos priorités? SI NO

Si oui, seriez-vous prêts à le démarrer? SI NO

Annex 4. Example of data sheets from OPROMAR vessel "A". All fish were identified as *M. polli*.

Caja A

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra			Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola	Longitud total (cm)					Latitud	Longitud
A1	x		635	H	28/11	03:30	410	18°36'395"N	016°54'198"W
A2	x		572	H	28/11	12:00	400	18°38'488"N	016°48'735"W
A3	x		399	J	28/11	09:30	390	19°02'912"N	016°54'611"W
A4									
A5	x		40	J	29/11	03:10	400	18°22'877"N	016°44'086"W
A6	x		58'6	H	29/11	08:25	380	18°33'809"N	016°42'959"W
A7	y		36'8	J	29/11	13:45	370	18°22'806"N	016°43'009"W
A8	x		40'2	J	29/11	19:10	360	18°37'574"N	016°47'404"W
A9									
A10	x		34'4	J	30/11	03:45	350	19°03'435"N	016°53'593"W
A11	x		63	H	30/11	13:45	390	18°38'498"N	016°47'695"W
A12	x		48'9	H	30/11	09:20	340	18°51'235"N	016°52'900"W
A13									
A14	x		59'8	H	01/12	01:15	360	19°03'614"N	016°54'095"W
A15	x		34'9	J	01/12	09:28	315	19°36'435"N	016°08'844"W
A16	v		44'8	M	01/12	16:50	370	19°42'511"N	017°04'481"W
A17									
A18	x		58'6	H	02/12	01:40	420	19°40'103"N	017°15'052"W
A19	v		49	H	02/12	12:30	420	19°41'937"N	017°04'205"W
A20									
A21	x		51'1	H	03/12	02:00	425	20°18'381"N	017°48'341"W
A22	v		45'6	M	03/12	08:00	360	19°32'425"N	017°53'082"W
A23									
A24	x		51'2	H	05/12	03:10	400	18°38'366"N	016°43'618"N
A25	v		47'8	H	05/12	08:30	380	18°22'671"N	016°43'338"W

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra			Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola	Longitud total (cm)					Latitud	Longitud
A26		x	56'4	H	05/12	15:40	370	18°03'084"N	016°38'659"W
A27									
A28		v	57	H	06/12	00:00	390	18°21'166"N	016°43'593"W
A29		v	49'4	H	06/12	05:35	410	18°03'675"N	016°39'797"W
A30		x	54'7	H	06/12	12:30	430	18°22'356"N	016°44'424"W
A31		v	46'8	M	06/12	19:50	385	18°03'353"N	016°39'007"W
A32									
A33		v	40'2	M	07/12	02:25	405	18°22'773"N	016°44'413"W
A34		x	43'5	H	07/12	08:00	400	18°37'458"N	016°48'572"W
A35		v	36	J	07/12	17:15	370	19°03'665"N	016°54'265"W
A36									
A37		x	55'2	H	08/12	02:10	410	18°38'475"N	016°49'083"W
A38		v	57'4	H	08/12	07:20	410	18°22'900"N	016°44'339"W
A39		x	32'8	J	08/12	11:30	90	18°40'317"N	016°27'726"W
A40		v	336	J	08/12	15:00	80	18°43'841"N	016°27'225"W
A41									
A42		v	54'1	H	09/12	00:40	350	19°03'039"N	016°53'864"W
A43		x	41	J	09/12	09:20	310	19°36'552"N	017°08'588"W
A44		x	39	J	09/12	14:40	330	19°36'401"N	017°08'851"W
A45		v	47	M	09/12	23:54	355	19°42'961"N	017°10'592"W
A46									
A47		v	40'5	J	12/12	09:00	400	20°26'923"N	017°53'390"W
A48		v	55'6	H	12/12	21:30	410	20°45'332"N	017°49'246"W
A49									
A50		x	58'6	H	13/12	06:00	390	20°23'193"N	017°50'388"W

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
A51			39	J	13/12	19:35	360	19°35'167"N	017°09'683"W
A52									
A53		✓	61'4	H	14/12	03:00	390	19°42'409"N	017°14'890"W
A54		✓	53'7	H	14/12	16:10	370	18°38'392"N	016°47'829"W
A55		✓	57'1	H	14/12	21:00	370	18°22'252"N	016°43'240"W
A56									
A57		✓	56	M	15/12	04:30	370	18°03'196"N	016°39'207"W
A58		✓	60'9	H	15/12	11:25	410	18°22'866"N	015°44'226"W
A59		✓	57'1	H	15/12	16:40	400	18°27'553"N	016°48'520"W
A60									
A61		✓	44'8	M	16/12	01:25	350	19°12'452"N	016°53'839"W
A62		✓	47'9	M	16/12	11:15	355	19°14'409"N	016°52'948"W
A63		✓	55'5	H	16/12	21:00	370	19°16'029"N	016°58'336"W
A64									
A65		✓	45'6	M	17/12	06:30	370	19°42'481"N	017°14'281"W
A66									
A67		✓	59'1	H	19/12	08:15	400	20°41'730"N	017°54'551"W
A68		✓	62	H	19/12	18:30	390	20°23'346"N	017°50'008"W
A69									
A70		✓	51'8	H	20/12	03:15	410	20°45'000"N	017°54'107"W
A71		✓	60'1	H	20/12	11:45	420	20°17'463"N	017°49'211"W
A72		✓	42	M	20/12	20:00	380	20°25'755"N	017°45'975"W
A73									
A74		✓	51	H	21/12	06:00	410	20°22'246"N	017°57'033"W
A75		✓	45'9	M	21/12	15:00	370	20°43'523"N	017°16'272"W

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
A76									
A77		✓	46	M	22/12	00:10	360	20°15'865"N	017°50'358"W
A78		✓	53'2	H	22/12	05:05	415	20°45'501"N	017°49'125"W
A79		✓	59'9	H	22/12	16:15	390	20°19'120"N	017°48'231"W
A80									
A81		✓	48'7	M	23/12	00:05	300	20°21'484"N	017°49'056"W

Caja B

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
B1	x		37'5	J	23/12	04:00	320	18°23'174"N	016°41'084"W
B2	x		38'4	M	23/12	11:00	350	18°23'555"N	016°41'541"W
B3	x		46'2	J	23/12	17:30	370	18°23'501"N	016°41'599"W
B4									
B5			36'9	J	24/12	01:00	320	18°40'505"N	016°41'509"W
B6									
B7	x		62'5	H	26/12	02:45	415	18°38'493"N	016°49'012"W
B8	x		57	H	26/12	08:30	360	18°22'820"N	016°42'916"W
B9	x		54'2	H	26/12	15:15	380	18°02'288"N	016°42'242"W
B10									
B11	x		42'5	H	27/12	07:05	370	18°22'245"N	016°42'465"W
B12	x		50'5	H	27/12	08:45	370	19°23'448"N	016°54'247"W
B13	x		54	H	27/12	17:30	380	19°23'478"N	016°48'222"W
B14									
B15	x		54'8	H	28/12	07:05	350	18°23'097"N	016°42'621"W
B16	x		53'5	H	28/12	04:15	335	18°38'098"N	016°46'776"W
B17									
B18	x		35	J	28/12	09:30	360	18°22'822"N	016°42'922"W
B19	x		64'2	H	28/12	16:35	420	18°23'633"N	016°40'131"W
B20	x		34'7	J	28/12	23:00	290	18°02'510"N	016°31'231"W
B21									
B22	x		33'8	J	29/12	05:10	300	17°44'741"N	016°41'605"W
B23	x		35'3	J	29/12	10:30	320	18°01'685"N	016°37'454"W
B24	x		58'1	H	29/12	16:00	400	18°02'539"N	016°41'154"W
B25									

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
B26	x		36	J	30/12	04:50	350	18°38'212"N	016°47'209"W
B27	x		35'1	J	30/12	09:00	90	18°41'892"N	016°36'452"W
B28	x		22'5	J	30/12	18:20	350	19°23'531"N	016°52'951"W
B29									
B30	x		47'1	H	02/01	17:30	370	18°38'646"N	016°47'909"W
B31	x		34'8	J	02/01	23:00	380	18°22'852"N	016°48'602"W
B32									
B33	x		31'5	J	03/01	05:50	355	18°02'980"N	016°38'391"W
B34	x		50'2	H	03/01	12:00	375	17°46'382"N	016°44'242"W
B35	x		33'5	J	03/01	17:30	350	18°02'189"N	016°38'193"W
B36									
B37	x		33	J	04/01	07:05	340	17°46'223"N	016°48'155"W
B38	x		34'2	J	04/01	05:05	330	18°01'785"N	016°37'744"W
B39	x		41'3	M	04/01	10:30	360	18°03'079"N	016°38'707"W
B40	x		35'7	J	04/01	17:35	385	18°23'212"N	016°43'622"W
B41									
B42	x		38	H	05/01	07:25	400	18°03'687"N	016°39'522"W
B43	x		34'2	J	05/01	06:20	280	17°46'365"N	016°44'771"W
B44	x		32'5	J	05/01	12:15	310	17°25'201"N	016°44'051"W
B45	x		31'1	J	05/01	20:20	300	17°03'623"N	016°50'429"W
B46									
B47	x		36'9	J	06/01	02:50	305	15°01'356"N	016°37'342"W
B48	x		34	J	06/01	00:00	330	18°23'653"N	016°42'429"W
B49	x		42'5	M	06/01	15:25	340	18°38'012"N	016°46'184"W
B50									

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra				Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola	Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil				Latitud	Longitud
B51	✓		48'1	H	07/01	00:35	350	19°03'52.7"N	016°55'9.74"W
B52		✓	41'3	J	07/01	06:00	290	19°03'47.3"N	016°10'24.6"W
B53									
B54		✓	62'2	H	09/01	01:00	415	18°38'56.4"N	016°49'17.9"W
B55		✓	53'9	H	09/01	09:45	360	18°22'9.49"N	016°40'7.73"W
B56		✓	57'1	H	09/01	16:50	375	18°03'11.1"N	016°35'6.03"W
B57		✓	61'9	H	09/01	23:00	340	18°02'9.47"N	016°35'16.0"W
B58									
B59		✓	53'3	H	10/01	06:00	320	18°23'6.28"N	016°42'28.2"W
B60		✓	39'9	J	10/01	11:55	345	18°38'26.3"N	016°47'1.45"W
B61		✓	38'7	J	10/01	17:35	320	18°23'28.8"N	016°41'88.5"W
B62									
B63		✓	46	M	10/01	23:35	310	18°47'17.0"N	016°39'16.7"W
B64									
B65		✓	56'1	H	11/01	03:15	385	18°37'6.40"N	016°48'05.6"W
B66		✓	47'2	M	11/01	08:00	360	18°50'9.82"N	016°53'00.2"W
B67		✓	42	J	11/01	12:00	350	19°03'4.66"N	016°53'7.74"W
B68		✓	43	J	11/01	19:45	300	18°40'0.15"N	016°45'6.61"W
B69									
B70		✓	49'1	H	12/01	02:30	350	18°54'0.56"N	016°53'0.30"W
B71		✓	57'3	H	12/01	08:55	370	18°38'4.97"N	016°47'8.24"W
B72									
B73		✓	40'5	J	12/01	13:45	330	18°39'5.41"N	016°46'7.24"W
B74									
B75		✓	48	H	12/01	22:00	380	19°03'3.75"N	016°54'3.38"W

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra				Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola	Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil				Latitud	Longitud
B76		✓	46'3	M	13/01	07:30	315	19°36'11.2"N	017°08'6.55"W
B77									
B78		✓	45'9	H	13/01	12:05	350	19°36'4.71"N	017°09'0.85"W
B79									
B80		✓	46'1	M	13/01	17:15	370	19°40'5.22"N	017°14'0.42"W
B81		✓	40'7	J	13/01	23:45	310	19°36'7.67"N	017°08'3.28"W

Annex 5. Data sheets from OPROMAR vessel "B". All sampled fish were identified morphologically as *M. senegalensis*.

Caja C

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
C1	X		49	H	04/12/2019	15:55	500	18° 45' N	016° 50' W
C2	X		47	H	11	11	11 X 11	11	11
C3	X		43	H	11	11	11	11	11
C4	X		44	H	11	11	11	11	11 11
C5	X		46	M	11	11	11	11	11
C6	X		42	M	11	11	11	11	11
C7	X		43	H	11	11	11	11	11
C8	X		43	M	11	11	11	11	11
C9	X		44	M	11	11	11	11	11
C10	X		53	H	11	11	11	11	11
C11	X		55	H	11	11	11	11	11
C12	X		59	H	11	11	11	11	11
C13	X		52	H	11	11	11	11	11
C14	X		51	H	11	11	11	11	11
C15	X		51,5	H	11	11	11	11	11
C16	X		47,5	H	11	11	11	11	11
C17	X		46	H	11	11	11	11	11
C18	X		50	H	11	11	11	11	11
C19	X				11	11	11	11	11
C20	X		46	M	11	11	11	11	11
C21	X		48	H	11	11	11	11	11
C22	X		52	M	11	11	11	11	11
C23	X		51,5	M	11	11	11	11	11
C24	X		50	M	11	11	11	11	11
C25	X		46	M	11	11	11	11	11

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
C26	X		43,6	M	04/12/2019	15:00h	500	18°45'N	016°50'W
C27	X		56	M	"	"	"	"	"
C28	X		29	J	05/12/2019	14:00h	540	18°18'	016°40'
C29	X		30,5	J	"	"	"	"	"
C30	X		35,5	J	"	"	"	"	"
C31	X		32,2	J	"	"	"	"	"
C32	X		32	J	"	"	"	"	"
C33	X		38	J	"	"	"	"	"
C34	X		31	J	"	"	"	"	"
C35	X		33	J	"	"	"	"	"
C36	X		30	J	"	"	"	"	"
C37	X		31	J	"	"	"	"	"
C38	X		33	J	"	"	"	"	"
C39	X		30	J	"	"	"	"	"
C40	X		31,5	J	"	"	"	"	"
C41	X		34	J	"	"	"	"	"
C42	X		48	H	18/12/2019	17:00h	560mts	18°47'	016°51'
C43	X		50	H	"	"	"	"	"
C44	X		44	M	"	"	"	"	"
C45	X		47	M	"	"	"	"	"
C46	X		50	H	"	"	"	"	"
C47	X		44	M	"	"	"	"	"
C48	X		48	H	"	"	"	"	"
C49	X		56,5	H	"	"	"	"	"
C50	X		32	J	"	"	"	"	"

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
C51	X		48	M	18/12/2019	17:06	560 m	18° 47'	016° 51'
C52	X		48	H	X				
C53	X		28,2	J	X				
C54	X		31,5	J					
C55	X		53,5	H					
C56	X		53	M					
C57	X		33	J					
C58	X		34	J					
C59	X		55	M					
C60	X		34	J					
C61	X		32	J					
C62	X		50	M					
C63	X		52,5	H					
C64	X		51,5	H					
C65	X		57	H					
C66	X		47	H					
C67	X		45	M					
C68	X		44,5	M					
C69	X		48	M					
C70	X		52,2	M					
C71	X		48	H					
C72	X		32	J					
C73	X		50,0	H					
C74	X		49,5	M					
C75	X		54	M					

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
C76	X		53,5	H	18/12/2019	17:04	560	18° 47'	016° 51'
C77	X		35,5	J					
C78	X		58	H					
C79	X		49	M					
C80	X		52,5	H					
C81	X		48	H					

Caja D

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
D1	H		46	M	20/12/2019	16:00	564	18°02'N	016°57'W
D2	H		49	M					
D3	H		46,5	H					
D4	H		59,5	H					
D5	H		31,5	J					
D6	H		49	H					
D7	H		65	H					
D8	H		52	M					
D9	H		55	M					
D10	H		48,5	H					
D11	H		31	J					
D12	H		47	H					
D13	H		53	H					
D14	H		31	J					
D15	H		49,5	M					
D16	H		32	J					
D17	H		48	H					
D18	H		51	H					
D19			VACÍO						
D20	H		47,5	H					
D21	H		32	J					
D22	H		29,5	J					
D23	H		56,5	M					
D24	H		47	H					
D25	H		31	J					

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
D26			54	H	20/12/2019	16:00	564	18°02'N	016°57'W
D27			20,5	J					
D28			46,3	M					
D29			48,5	H					
D30			51	H					
D31			53,5	H					
D32			50,2	M					
D33			31	J					
D34			33,5	J					
D35			30,2	J					
D36			50	M					
D37			31,8	J					
D38			45	M					
D39			50	M					
D40			47	M					
D41			32,7	J	29/12/2019	19:00	512	20°28'N	017°50'W
D42			43,5	H					
D43			43,3	H					
D44			47,5	H					
D45			35	J					
D46			45,7	M					
D47			47,5	M					
D48			39,5	J					
D49			30,5	J					
D50			36	J					

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
D51	u	v	31,5	J	19/12/2019	19:00	512	20° 28' N	017° 50' W
D52	u	u	34,5	J	u	u	u	u	u
D53	u	u	33,5	J	u	u	u	u	u
D54	u	u	51,5	H	u	u	u	u	u
D55	u	u	47,2	M	u	u	u	u	u
D56	u	u	34,7	J	u	u	u	u	u
D57	u	u	48	M	u	u	u	u	u
D58	u	u	45	H	u	u	u	u	u
D59	u	u	52	M	u	u	u	u	u
D60	u	u	35	J	u	u	u	u	u
D61	u	u	35	J	u	u	u	u	u
D62	u	u	46,8	M	u	u	u	u	u
D63	u	u	51	H	u	u	u	u	u
D64	u	u	33	J	u	u	u	u	u
D65	u	u	43	H	u	u	u	u	u
D66	u	u	35,5	J	u	u	u	u	u
D67	u	u	44,5	M	u	u	u	u	u
D68	u	u	36	J	u	u	u	u	u
D69	u	u	53	M	u	u	u	u	u
D70	u	u	33,5	J	u	u	u	u	u
D71	u	u	47	H	u	u	u	u	u
D72	u	u	33,5	J	u	u	u	u	u
D73	u	u	46,7	M	u	u	u	u	u
D74	u	u	47	M	u	u	u	u	u
D75	u	u	33	J	u	u	u	u	u

Tubo	Especie de merluza negra		Longitud total (cm)	Sexo: M = macho H = hembra J = juvenil	Fecha	Hora	Profundidad (m)	Ubicación	
	<i>M. senegalensis</i> : "la senegalensis", merluza de Senegal	<i>M. polli</i> : "la polli", merluza de Angola						Latitud	Longitud
D76	u	u	33,5	J	20/12/2019	19:00	512	20° 28' N	017° 50' W
D77	u	u	31,5	J	u	u	u	u	u
D78	u	u	31	J	u	u	u	u	u
D79	u	u	52	M	u	u	u	u	u
D80	u	u	33	J	u	u	u	u	u
D81	u	u	32	J	u	u	u	u	u

Annex 6. Examples of DNA results for the analysed samples. Note: these are just the first two pages of a total of 43.

Tube ID	Morphological ID	Total length (cm)	Sex: M= male F= female J= juvenile	Date	Hour	Depth (m)	Fleet: OPROMAR PI =Industrial PA= Artisanal	Latitude	Longitude	DNA IDENTIFICATION_CR	Mislabeling
A01	M. polli	63.5	H	11/28/2019	3:30	410	OPROMAR	18.60658333	-16.9033	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A02	M. polli	57.2	H	11/28/2019	12:00	400	OPROMAR	18.64146667	-16.8127166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A03	M. polli	39.9	J	11/28/2019	9:30	390	OPROMAR	19.04853333	-16.9101833	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A04							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A05	M. polli	40	J	11/29/2019	3:10	400	OPROMAR	18.38128333	-16.7347666	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A06	M. polli	58.6	H	11/29/2019	8:25	380	OPROMAR	18.63015	-16.7993166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A07	M. polli	36.8	J	11/29/2019	13:45	370	OPROMAR	18.3801	-16.7168166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A08	M. polli	40.2	J	11/29/2019	19:10	360	OPROMAR	18.63123333	-16.7900666	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A09							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A10	M. polli	34.4	J	11/30/2019	3:45	350	OPROMAR	19.05808333	-16.8982166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A11	M. polli	63	H	11/30/2019	13:45	370	OPROMAR	18.64163333	-16.7949166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A12	M. polli	48.9	H	11/30/2019	9:20	340	OPROMAR	18.85391667	-16.882	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A13							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A14	M. polli	59.8	H	12/1/2019	1:15	360	OPROMAR	19.06023333	-16.9015833	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A15	M. polli	34.9	J	12/1/2019	9:28	315	OPROMAR	19.6073	-16.1474	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A16	M. polli	44.8	M	12/1/2019	16:50	370	OPROMAR	19.70851667	-17.2358	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A17							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A18	M. polli	58.6	H	12/2/2019	1:40	400	OPROMAR	19.70305	-17.2542166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A19	M. polli	49	H	12/2/2020	12:30	420	OPROMAR	19.69895	-17.2554666	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A20							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A21	M. polli	51.1	H	12/3/2019	2:00	405	OPROMAR	20.30635	-17.8056833	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A22	M. polli	45.6	M	12/3/2020	8:00	360	OPROMAR	20.55616667	-17.8847	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A23							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A24	M. polli	51.2	H	12/5/2019	3:10	400	OPROMAR	18.63943333	-16.8103	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A25	M. polli	47.8	H	12/5/2019	8:30	380	OPROMAR	18.37785	-16.7223	<i>M. polli</i>	No

Tube ID	Morphological ID	Total length (cm)	Sex: M= male F= female J= juvenile	Date	Hour	Depth (m)	Fleet: OPROMAR PI =Industrial PA= Artisanal	Latitude	Longitude	DNA IDENTIFICATION_CR	Mislabeling
A26	M. polli	56.4	H	12/5/2019	15:40	370	OPROMAR	18.0514	-16.6443166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A27							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A28	M. polli	57	H	12/6/2019	0:00	390	OPROMAR	18.3661	-16.72655	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A29	M. polli	49.4	H	12/6/2019	5:35	410	OPROMAR	18.06125	-16.6632833	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A30	M. polli	54.7	H	12/6/2019	12:30	430	OPROMAR	18.3726	-16.7404	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A31	M. polli	46.8	M	12/6/2019	19:50	385	OPROMAR	18.05588333	-16.6501166	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A32							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A33	M. polli	40.2	M	12/7/2020	2:25	405	OPROMAR	18.37955	-16.7402166	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A34	M. polli	43.5	H	12/7/2020	8:00	400	OPROMAR	18.6243	-16.8095333	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A35	M. polli	36	J	12/7/2020	17:15	370	OPROMAR	19.06108333	-16.9044166	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A36							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A37	M. polli	55.2	H	12/8/2020	2:10	410	OPROMAR	18.64125	-16.81805	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A38	M. polli	57.4	H	12/8/2020	7:20	410	OPROMAR	18.38166667	-16.7389833	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A39	M. polli	32.8	J	12/8/2020	11:30	90	OPROMAR	18.67195	-16.6287666	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A40	M. polli	33.6	J	12/8/2020	15:00	80	OPROMAR	18.73068333	-16.6222666	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A41							OPROMAR	0	0	-	
A42	M. polli	54.1	H	12/9/2019	0:40	350	OPROMAR	19.05065	-16.8977333	<i>M. polli</i>	No
A43	M. polli	41	J	12/9/2020	9:20	310	OPROMAR	19.6092	-17.1431333	<i>M. senegalensis</i>	Yes
A44	M. polli	39	J	12/9/2019	14:40	330	OPROMAR	19.60668333	-17.1475166	<i>M. polli</i>	No

